

AI4

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Communication, training, outreach, dissemination and collaboration liaison and exploitation plans

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose

An exploitation and dissemination plan is an important part of any research project, and it is particularly important for a project like AI4EOSC that aims to promote the use of AI tools and services within the EOSC. A well-designed communication and dissemination plan can help to ensure that the project's goals and achievements are widely known and understood by key audiences, and that the project's results are used and applied in ways that maximize their potential impact and benefits to society.

The purpose of such a plan is to promote the project's goals and achievements, to create synergies and coordinate activities with other initiatives and projects, and to ensure the impact of the project through industrial and scientific collaboration and outreach and training. This plan will be updated consequent at months 12 and 24 (deliverables D2.1a and D2.1b).

1.2 Document organization

This document outlines how the project's results will be used and shared with key audiences, in order to maximize their potential impact and benefits.

The [Exploitation Plan](#) section outlines the objectives and methodology for exploiting the project's results, including the exploitable results that will be generated by the project and the roles and responsibilities of project partners in managing and exploiting these outputs. The section also includes information about the activities that will be carried out to support the exploitation of the project's results, such as training and capability building, IPR management, and managing exploitation results. The section also describes the methods that will be used to monitor the progress and success of the exploitation plan.

The [Dissemination Plan](#) section outlines the objectives and methodology for disseminating information about the project and its results to key audiences. It includes information about the target audience for the project's results, as well as the roles and responsibilities of project partners in disseminating information about the project. The section also describes the instruments and channels that will be used to share information about the project, such as the project's website, social media channels, and events. The section also includes information about how the effectiveness of the dissemination plan will be monitored.

Finally, the document includes [annexes](#) with additional information, such as definitions of key terms and the branding kit for the project.

EXPLOITATION PLAN

2.1 Objectives and methodology

The exploitation goal is to support promotion of AI4EOSC results and their use to maximize the expected impacts of the project. This section will therefore outline the actions that are to be taken to make use of the project results for scientific and commercial purposes in further research activities beyond those covered in AI4EOSC project use cases.

The exploitation plan for the AI4EOSC project will be implemented with the following principles:

1. **Publishing project results under open licenses** aiming at open source software developments and the delivery of operational services that can be exploited following the cloud computing service model.
2. **Engaging stakeholders** by the customisation of proposed solutions in the selected use cases and reaching external ones (e.g. exploitation activities in R&D projects like EGI-ACE or iMagine).
3. **Delivering services with easy adaptation/integration** achieved by the provisioning of new high-level services and functionalities.
4. **Targeting long term exploitation** by integrating project outputs:
 - a. into upstream software products.
 - b. into use case related products (e.g. integration with the existing national agriculture platform in case of Polish use case).
 - c. into the more global architecture of EOSC, and the AlonDemand (AloD) ecosystem.
5. **Using the project results also for academic purposes** (Master, PhD, post-PhD) supported by several academic partners that have already developed key components used in the production EU e-Infrastructures.

2.2 Exploitable results

We have identified five initial Key Exploitable Results (KER), that are described below, that will be monitored and updated during project lifetime. Exploitable results, as well as the relevant stakeholders and the possible exploitation plans are listed below, and are being tracked on the project confluence under the link:

<https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Key+Exploitable+Results>.

During the course of the project we will also, as part of the exploitation and innovation management, analyze and try to identify any other exploitable results and will describe them in a similar way.

Table 1. KER1: AI4EOSC Platform

Result type	Software and services
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URL	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/object_id=&type=&anchor=&sort=_score&q=ai4eosc
Key innovation	Next generation AI platform implementing advanced features such as federated or split learning.
Target audiences	Researchers, AI service providers
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Generic-value service, allowing scientists to develop and service applications easily
Key exploitation paths	Exploitation through the EOSC Portal (free basis during project lifetime). Subscription-based, pay per data volume or individual contract to adapt the service.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require Intellectual Property (IP) transfer.
Result description	Modular, reusable, integrable, composable set of components integrated into a pilot platform. EOSC-based cloud platform will allow developing machine learning and deep learning applications that require distributed and federated learning as well as composite scenarios in order to build more complex applications and models.
Result Maturity	TRL 8
Do you already have customers for this result?	Built on the top of the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud outcomes and the EOSC compute platform and services (https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/deepaas-training-facility), customers are the current EOSC users that discover services from a variety of different providers.
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.
Which Business Sectors do your customers mainly come from?	Engineering & Technology, Natural Sciences, Generic Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, Humanities, Social Sciences, ...

Unique value proposition	The project facilitates the development of new techniques and methodologies to effectively exploit large, distributed and heterogeneous datasets by researchers in the upcoming years, anticipating the needs of complex AI applications.
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Table 2. KER2: AI4EOSC Platform Customization

Result type	Software and services, Business Models
Key innovation	Reduced time-to-market for SME and industry developing AI/ML/DL applications, private platform or platforms to build a service.
Target audiences	Service providers, SMEs, innovators, start-ups
Key benefit (for the audiences)	More and better services for faster and higher quality on-premises deployments, automated and customized platforms tailored to specific stakeholder needs.
Key exploitation paths	Depending on the specific case, it could be subscription-based, pay per data volume or pay for deployment of the service.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.
Result description	Customization paths for the AI4EOSC platform across multiple Cloud back-ends using the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator together with the Infrastructure Manager. Extension to the existing DEEP platform in order to ease the customization path both for researchers and for the exploitation of the deployed services.
Result Maturity	TRL 8
Do you already have customers for this result?	AI4EOSC communities
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.

Unique value proposition	Support the data management solution needed by the AI4EOSC communities in order to better deploy services and applications leveraging the data-aware placement functionalities of the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator.
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Table 3. KER3: AI4EOSC Catalogue

Result type	AI models, Software and services
URL	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?object_id=&type=&anchor=&sort=_score&q=ai4eosc
Key innovation	Increased service offer and capabilities beyond the present landscape in addressing the current and anticipated needs of the research community at large.
Target audiences	Researchers, SMEs, innovators, start-ups
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Services addressing the current and anticipated needs of the research community at large.
Key exploitation paths	Individual contracts for using or adapting the application.
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses, other assets with CC-BY.
Result description	<p>Delivery of a public catalog of services following the layered cloud service model (IaaS, PaaS, FaaS, SaaS) exploiting in a structural way resources coming from these different layers in the cloud based EOSC resources.</p> <p>Providing rich services to build and deploy customizable machine learning, deep learning and artificial intelligence applications following a platform and serverless approach with horizontal scalability over the EOSC continuum.</p>
Result Maturity	TRL 8

Do you already have customers for this result?	Services can be customized and integrated in the existing workflows of researchers across different disciplines.
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.
Unique value proposition	Immediate adoption of an application that has provided a usable solution in a similar case.

Table 4. KER4: AI4EOSC Exchange

Result type	Policies and best practices
Key innovation	Transforming the way the audience create, share and exploit research outputs (data, publications, protocols, methodologies, software, code, etc.) within and across research disciplines, leading to better quality, validation, more innovation and higher productivity of research.
Target audiences	Researchers, educators, EOSC and AI4EU communities, Digital innovation Hubs (DIHs), Policy Makers, Private companies
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Improvement in AI/ML/DL development for research, innovation providing readiness to exploit EOSC assets.
Key exploitation paths	Expertise and consultancy services, individual contracts.
IPR approach	Offered with an open license. Consultancy as a service, no IP transfer.
Result description	An EOSC AI exchange and community of practice around AI/ML/DL application development and deployment at scale, including but not limited to a noticeable knowledge body in the form of best practices, documentation and publications.
What type of customers/ users do you have?	Researchers, service providers from different areas.

Which Business Sectors do your customers mainly come from?	Engineering & Technology, Natural Sciences, Generic Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, Humanities, Social Sciences
Unique value proposition	Co-design activities from the early beginning of the project development phases. The consortium has proven experience on fostering DevOps practices in order to better cooperate with user communities thus providing an easy path towards the effective deployment of the developed tools.

Table 5. KER5: AI4EOSC Models and technological solutions

Result type	Software and services
Key innovation	Integrating use cases results with commercial products or well established public platforms.
Target audiences	SMEs, innovators, startups, research communities and AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers. Public domain, initiatives in agriculture and environmental protection.
Key benefit (for the audiences)	Wider adoption of AI/ML/DL techniques for non-practitioners to provide insights on scientific data.
Key exploitation paths	Depending on the specific case, it could be subscription-based, pay per data volume or pay for deployment of the service.
IPR approach	Software tools that will be delivered in the portal are based on open source licenses.
Result description	Domain specific AI models and technological solutions for the leading use cases (e.g. in agriculture, thermography) targeted for direct exploitation by scientists and scientific teams.
Result Maturity	TRL 7
Do you already have customers for this result?	Yes, we have (e.g. integrating UC2 from WODR in eDWIN)

Unique value proposition	Application of ML/DL technologies use cases results to provide solutions for economic and societal sectors.
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2.3 Roles and responsibilities

In relation to specific consortium members assignment, the results exploitation will be particularly covered by WP2. As this Work Package leader, PSNC will support the innovation and exploitation activities of the project.

The key roles in the results management and exploitation of AI4EOSC project and their responsibilities are as follows:

WP leaders

- To register and update project results on AI4EOSC Software repository: <https://github.com/AI4EOSC>.
- To ensure that dissemination and exploitation plans are defined by the main responsible of the result.

Main Responsible of PR

- In collaboration with the WP leader, registration of information on the project results in the exploitation Confluence workspace, including exploitation and dissemination plans.
- To provide input on the work performed, achievements, problems encountered, unexpected risks and corrective actions taken, deviations from the original Description of the Action.
- To Advise on the best approach to protect IPR produced during the project.

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- To review periodically the list of aggregated results.
- Validation of the key exploitable results, and review the dissemination and exploitation plan execution.

Project coordinator

- Collect, review and submit deliverables.

2.4 Activities

This section presents exploitation activities recognized in the beginning of the project, that aim at further maximizing the impact of the project results. It covers the description of tutorials and training, management of IPR and exploitation outputs that adhere to the FAIR data and research principle.

Training and capability building

One of the important activities that will facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of the project results is knowledge transfer in the form of the training.

Prepared training courses and materials will cover different results of the projects including the Key Exploitable Results.

The approach for the training and capabilities building is to:

- To perform exploitation through EOSC with freemium approach and consultancy.
- To integrate, as tutorials, real use cases results with established public platforms.
- To create the training courses and materials in the form of technical, downloadable results, but also consultancy building on training on knowledge transfer.

As a result, the audience will benefit from access to practical guidelines that help to develop services both secure and of high quality. This way a smooth integration into the AI4EOSC services of researchers, service providers SMEs, start-ups and industry will be fully supported.

AI4EOSC for the purpose of training will follow the EOSC-Synergy project approach and will reuse tools developed and deployed in this project for the EOSC ecosystem and maintained by PSNC. We expect to provide the MOOC Courses that will focus on usage of the results of the project, as well as in person tutorials provided in conjunction with organized events. AI4EOSC will use Learn@Synergy platform that consist of Modular set of tools for preparing and conducting tutorials (<https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/>:

- MOOC: customised Moodle
- Videoconference facility for trainings: based on eduMEET
- Interactive computing: based on Jupyter Notebook
- Training material catalogue (<https://learn.eosc-synergy.eu/catalogue/>)

In addition the platform already includes several courses related to EOSC, but also it contains the Guidance and best practice for creating good quality tutorials.

Figure 1. Learn@Synergy platform - handbook page

Next updated deliverable will include the specific timeline of the courses to be delivered in the form of the MOOC.

IPR management

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) should be defined for each project result that could be protected with patents, copyright, design rights, database rights, trademarks, non-disclosure agreements, utility models and petty patents.

Services delivered on AI4EOSC project can be exploited by industrial partners to build their own machine learning and artificial intelligence applications having IPR setting for their own developments defined. Therefore, the IPR definition shall minimize the risk of IP-related service disruptions.

Undoubtedly, indicating participating partners' roles to set IPR definition according to their specific expertise and the foreground generated during the project activities is necessary.

Table 6. IPR project roles

KER	AI4EOSC Platform	AI4EOSC Platform Customization	AI4EOSC Catalogue	AI4EOSC Exchange	AI4EOSC Models and technological solutions
Owner	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime	joint-ownership by AI4EOSC Consortium, to be further discussed and agreed during project lifetime
IPR approach	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.	Project software based on open source licenses. Service offer does not require IP transfer.	Project software based on open source licenses, other assets with CC-BY.	Offered with an open license. Consultancy as a service, no IP transfer	Software tools that will be delivered in the portal are based on open source licenses.

Managing exploitation results

As the project's outputs will be fully defined, exploitation opportunities will be assessed as part of the exploitation management. For each of the key asset appropriate strategies will be defined for its exploitation.

Set of activities for identified exploitation opportunities will be performed aiming at effective exploitation of the project results. The responsible WP2 in cooperation with all partners will

maintain and elaborate the dissemination and exploitation strategy plan in collaboration to develop an appropriate business plan(s).

2.5 Monitoring

The Lean Canvas method² was used as a basis to create the template used to depict key exploitable results in section 2.2 *Exploitable results* and prepare the exploitation/business plan for an exploitable result. Continuous updates to this adjusted form will help to focus on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages.

² Maurya, A. (2010). Why Lean Canvas vs Business Model Canvas? Practice Trumps Theory.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

3.1 Objectives and methodology

This section describes a set of actions to ensure that the project's results are effectively communicated to relevant audiences, including other researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

The dissemination plan will outline the steps that will be taken to share the project's findings. It will involve identifying key target groups and developing a strategy to make these groups aware of the project's results and encourage adoption.

The dissemination plan for the AI4EOSC project will be implemented in three phases:

- I. **Launch campaign** (months 1-3): During this phase, the consortium had publicized the start of the project and its objectives, using the [project website](#), social media (such as Twitter, Mastodon and YouTube), and other communication materials to generate interest and promote it among stakeholders. The consortium also developed visual identity and communication materials, such as brochures and posters, to create a consistent and cohesive brand for the project (see [Annex II](#) for further details).
- II. **Creation of awareness and engagement campaign** (months 3-15): In this phase, the consortium will present the approach to develop the platform and services to specialized audiences from the scientific community and industrial stakeholders, collecting feedback and further needs. This will involve organizing workshops and events where the project's results can be showcased and discussed with potential users and adopters. The consortium will also identify and establish potential partnerships with DIHs and SMEs, which will be involved in co-creation pilots to test and evaluate the project's results.
- III. **Promotion campaign** (months 15-36): This final phase will focus on promoting the project's results to relevant scientific and industry stakeholders, supporting the exploitation strategy of the project. The specifics of this promotion phase will be defined more specifically as the project progresses, based on the results of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 and the identification of stakeholders. This will involve using a wide range of tactics, from publishing articles in relevant scientific journals and presenting at conferences and workshops, to promote the project's results and engage with potential adopters. The consortium will also use social media and other online platforms to reach a wider audience and increase awareness of the project's results.

The AI4EOSC project will follow a segmented approach to disseminating its results. This means that the consortium will identify specific target groups and develop tailored strategies to reach and engage with these groups.

To maximize the impact of the project's dissemination material for end users, the AI4EOSC project will prioritize the translation of selected key resources into national languages. This will ensure that the project's information and resources are accessible to a wider audience, including those who may not speak English as their first language.

3.2 Target audience

The AI4EOSC project has identified several target groups that it will aim to reach and engage with through its dissemination strategy and liaisons. These target groups are described below.

- **Research communities:** The project aims to motivate the research community to engage with the EOSC portal and the new services and functionalities developed within the project. This could include researchers working in various fields, such as agriculture, biomedicine, and energy, who are especially interested in finding new ways to use AI/ML/DL tools and services more effectively.
- **AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers:** The project aims to raise awareness of the availability of AI/ML/DL tools and services in the EOSC ecosystem and encourage their adoption by practitioners and developers working in these fields. This could include data scientists, machine learning engineers, and software developers who are looking for ways to build and deploy AI/ML/DL applications at scale.
- **Similar technological platforms and initiatives:** The project aims to promote interoperability and establish partnerships/liasons with other platforms and initiatives (e.g. AI4Europe and the AI-on-Demand Platform) that offer similar services and also with service providers promoting easy installation and integration on the platform.
The EOSC ecosystem: The project aims to raise awareness of the integration and availability of AI/ML/DL services in the EOSC portal and promote the AI4EOSC exchange with existing applications. This could include stakeholders within the EOSC ecosystem, such as service providers, data managers, and researchers, who are looking for ways to more effectively use and benefit from the EOSC(e.g. TF Technical Interoperability of Data and Services). In addition project members participate in relevant EOSC Task Forces to promote the technologies and results of the project in EOSC. **Other projects exploiting AI solutions:** AI4EOSC will strive to foster additional collaborations with ongoing initiatives leveraging AI solutions, like iImagine (AI-based image tools for aquatic sciences) or FlexiGroBots (AI for intelligent automation of precision agriculture) EU projects.
- **Education:** The project aims to integrate AI4EOSC knowledge and solutions into data science curricula and courses. This could include educators and students who are interested in learning about the latest developments in AI/ML/DL and how to apply these technologies in their work.
- **Digital innovation Hubs (DIHs):** The project aims to extend the DIHs' portfolio of offers with AI4EOSC services and consultancy, and establish new collaborations through this channel. This could include DIHs that are looking for ways to offer new AI/ML/DL services to their customers and partners.
- **SMEs, innovators, startups:** The project aims to foster the uptake of the project's products by these groups, to support the exploitation of the project's use cases. This could include small and medium-sized enterprises, innovators, and startups who are

looking for ways to incorporate AI/ML/DL technologies into their products and services.

- **General public and the media:** The project also aims at reaching the broader society via the media and will try to establish solid ties with both specialized and generalist media.

Following the segmented approach presented in the previous section, a tailored set of actions are defined to follow specific dissemination strategies for each of the target audiences. These strategies are presented below.

To engage with research communities and AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers, the AI4EOSC project has established a comprehensive set of case studies that demonstrate the successful use of the resources developed by the project. These case studies will be featured on the project's website and will serve as a key component of our dissemination and communication efforts, including social media campaigns, webinars, and events.

The case studies will provide concrete examples of how researchers can benefit from using the resources developed by EOSC, as well as how service providers can directly benefit from offering services and resources through the EOSC portal. To further showcase the capabilities of the AI4EOSC platform, the project will also provide demonstrations of the platform at relevant workshops and generate showcases for various domains. These efforts will help to highlight the value and potential of the AI4EOSC resources to research communities and AI/ML/DL practitioners and application developers.

To engage with similar technological platforms, the consortium will establish direct contacts with relevant platforms and seek to share knowledge and identify common points of collaboration. This will involve actively seeking out opportunities to engage with these platforms and establish partnerships that can help to promote interoperability and facilitate the exchange of ideas and resources. By establishing these relationships and fostering collaboration, the project aims to increase the reach and impact of its resources and contribute to the development of the broader AI/ML/DL ecosystem.

The AI4EOSC project will coordinate its dissemination efforts with the communication teams of EOSC-related initiatives (e.g. EOSC Association, EOSC Future and its follow-ups) in order to engage with the EOSC ecosystem. Through these partnerships, the project will be able to disseminate its results and updates through the existing communication channels of these initiatives, including social media, the EOSC portal's community updates, events, and news. This coordinated approach will help to ensure that the project's information and resources are directly shared with the EOSC ecosystem and can be accessed by stakeholders within the ecosystem, such as service providers, data managers, and researchers.

The project aims to engage with the Education audience by making direct contacts with universities and participating in selected educational events. This includes establishing partnerships with institutions that offer relevant courses (e.g. Master in Data Science

UC/UIMP³ or an Introduction to Data Science course FIIT STU⁴) and collaborating with educators to integrate AI4EOSC knowledge and solutions into their curricula. In addition, the project will invite relevant stakeholders from the Education sector to participate in its advisory board, providing a platform for ongoing dialogue and collaboration. By engaging in these ways, the project hopes to promote the adoption of AI/ML/DL technologies in education and to support the next generation of data scientists and AI practitioners.

Regarding Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), the AI4EOSC project will establish collaborations and partnerships with relevant DIHs (e.g EOSC DIH, EUHubs4Data, smartAgriHubs) and clusters through existing links with project partners. This strategy is intended to make the projects' services and consultancy offerings available to DIHs and to encourage the adoption and integration of these resources into their portfolio of offerings.

In order to foster the uptake of the different products developed by AI4EOSC among SME, innovators and startups, our communication efforts will be targeted toward these groups, with a focus in disseminating the use-cases developed by the project partners through events and webinars specific use-cases sectors. Other actions include engaging with projects and hubs such as European Lab for Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS) to gain visibility among their members, and leveraging the established network of collaboration switch DIHs to multiply the impact of the outreach efforts outreach potential interested parties. These efforts will be aimed at raising awareness of AI4EOSC products and encouraging their adoption by SME, innovators and startups.

3.3 Roles and responsibilities

It should be noted that all members of the consortium will be involved to a greater or lesser extent in the tasks related to the impact of the project. The Work Package (WP) leader is PSNC.

All partners are open to collaborate and participate in any dissemination task, but different partners will be responsible for coordinating the efforts for each task.

- CSIC will act as the moderator of the AI4EOSC Project social media profiles, controlling and filtering content and monitoring the impact of the information uploaded.
- The website will be developed and maintained by Predictia, updating the website pages with the latest events and news.

However, given that information to be communicated is to come from all partner institutions, it's necessary that all partners contribute to the social media and website effort and provide input.

³ <https://masterdatascience.ifca.es/>

⁴ <https://github.com/FIIT-IAU/2021-2022>

3.4 Instruments and channels

Website

The AI4EOSC project website, hosted on ai4eosc.eu, serves as a central hub for the dissemination of information about our project and the work that we are doing to develop and provide advanced Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning services to the research community through the European Open Science Cloud. The website will also include a section for training materials.

Figure 2. Screenshot of AI4EOSC project's website.

On the website, you can learn more about the partners, goals and objectives of the AI4EOSC project, as well as stay up-to-date with the latest events and news related to AI4EOSC. You can also access all deliverables, scientific publications and media appearances.

Social networks

Social media has undoubtedly become one of the most important tools people resort to in order to find and/or spread information – from average citizens or private companies to government officials or institutions. It's a powerful tool to reach out to specialized sectors too, and media increasingly use it as a source.

In addition to serving as a tool for communication and dissemination, our social media presence would allow us to build a community of followers and engage in dialogue with stakeholders.

The AI4EOSC Project will regularly use Twitter, Mastodon and YouTube. In [Section 3.5](#), a list of Key Performance Indicators is proposed for monitoring the different social media networks (see Table 2).

Twitter ([@AI4EOSC](https://twitter.com/AI4EOSC))

The use of Twitter will be focused on communicating AI4EOSC news, events, calls and partners activity.

Suggested hashtag for all the informations: **#AI4EOSC**

Mastodon (<https://mastodon.social/@ai4eosc>)

It's still at an early stage, but it will be used as a complementary tool to expand the reach of the Twitter account.

YouTube ([@ai4eosc](https://www.youtube.com/@ai4eosc))

This account will showcase the explanatory animation movie, the latest news about the project, and other audiovisual materials.

Animation Video

A two-minute explanatory video on the project is in the making. It will be made available via the project website and a YouTube channel.

Events

As part of the dissemination management several events have been identified as opportunities for dissemination of the results. Those include the scientific conferences, exhibitions, policy meetings and domain specific events. The list is included in the dedicated confluence page and most significant events are listed on the website in the Events & News section. In the [Annex III](#) below we include a snapshot of the Events table, presenting opportunities for 2023.

Others

A Zenodo community has been created at <https://zenodo.org/communities/ai4eosc/> for researchers under the AI4EOSC project who want to increase the visibility of their research outputs (journal articles, presentations, datasets, models and others), collaborate with other researchers, and ensure the quality of their research outputs.

3.5 Monitoring

Monitoring is a key section of a dissemination plan because it allows organizations to track the effectiveness of their dissemination efforts and make any necessary adjustments.

By monitoring the reach and impact of their dissemination efforts, organizations can ensure that they are effectively communicating their messages and achieving their goals. For example, if an organization is using a dissemination plan to promote a new product or service, monitoring can help them track how many people are hearing about the project results and whether or not they are taking action as a result of the dissemination efforts.

Table 7. List of Key Performance Indicators for the dissemination plan.

Metric	Number of occurrences
Publications exploiting the AI4EOOSC framework	5
Public services available based on AI4EOOSC exchange applications	5
User workshops held	3
Collaborations with external industries, including SMEs	5
External use cases on-boarded	5
External user communities using AI4EOOSC platform	5

A set of specific actions will be taken to achieve this objective, among which the following stand out:

- **Setting goals and metrics:** The project establishes clear goals and metrics for the dissemination plan, such as the number of stakeholders reached, the number of interactions with stakeholders, and the number of adoption of the project's results. These goals and metrics could be used to track progress and determine the success of the dissemination plan. Table 1 sets out the objectives committed to by the consortium. In particular, a set of specific indicators for monitoring social media activity is described in Table 2.
- **Regular evaluation:** The consortium will conduct regular evaluations of the dissemination plan to assess its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. This could involve conducting surveys or interviews with stakeholders to gather feedback on the plan and its impact.
- **Engagement tracking:** The project could track engagement with stakeholders through various channels, such as social media, email, and events. This could provide insight into the reach and impact of the dissemination plan and help to identify successful approaches and areas for improvement.
- **Adaptation:** The project could adapt the dissemination plan based on feedback from stakeholders and the results of evaluations. This could involve updating the plan to reflect changing needs and priorities, as well as incorporating new approaches and techniques for reaching and engaging with stakeholders.

Table 8. List of specific Key Performance Indicators for social media channels.

Indicator	Number of occurrences
Followers across all social networks	750
Average of messages per month in Twitter	10
Average of messages per month in Mastodon	10
Videos published in Youtube by the end of the project	15

As part of the monitoring process we have setup the registry of all the publications, blog posts, social posts, it is being collected on the internal confluence

(<https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Dissemination+table>) and in [Annex IV](#) we include the snapshot of the activities since the beginning of the project.

ANNEXES

I. Definitions

The Definitions Annex of the dissemination and exploitation plan for the AI4EOSC project includes the following definitions of key terms:

- **DIH:** It refers to the Digital Innovation Hub.
- **EOSC:** The European Open Science Cloud is a digital infrastructure that brings together existing scientific data and services from across Europe, making it easier for researchers to access, share, and reuse data in their work.
- **IPR:** It stands for "Intellectual Property Rights." In the context of the AI4EOSC project, this term refers to the legal rights that protect the project's results, such as patents, copyrights, and trademarks. These rights are important for ensuring that the project's results can be used and exploited in a way that is fair and beneficial to all project partners.
- **KER:** It refers to the Key Exploitable Results of a project.
- **SME:** It refers to Small and Medium-sized Enterprises that are defined in the [EU recommendation 2003/361](#).
- **TRL:** It refers to the Technology Readiness Levels which is a measure of maturity for a technology or a project. A total of nine different levels are defined where the level 9 corresponds to a system proven in an operational environment.

II. Branding Kit

The visual identity of the AI4EOSC project is built on the following materials:

Logo:

Logo variations:

For more logo variations please visit: <https://ai4eosc.eu/communication-kit/>

Font:

The chosen font for the project is Roboto Regular. It guarantees good readability.

Uppercase

Lowercase

A B C D E F G H I J K
L M N O P Q R S T U
V W X Y Z

a b c d e f g h i j k l
m n o p q r s t u v w
x y z

Colors:

The two official brand colors for the EOSC logo are mild pink and lively emerald.

The color codes are as follows:

Pink

RGB 255/92/128

CMYK 0/76/27/0

#ff5b7f

Green

RGB 0/134/145

CMYK 90/0/33/25

#008792

For more color variations, please download the Co-Branding Guidelines at:
https://ai4eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/10/2023/02/20220614_EOSC_Co-Branding-Guidelines_1_EOSC-A.pdf

III. Events Table

Event Name	Date	Type (International/ National) Symposium/ Conference/ Workshop/ Seminar/Fair)	Deadlines	Location	Opportunity description	URL
EOSC Symposium 2023		Symposium			The main EOSC annual event. Stakeholders from ministries, policy makers, research performing organisations, service providers, research infrastructures and research communities across Europe and beyond are expected to attend the Symposium to reflect on the EOSC key achievements and strategic challenges and to identify priorities and concrete actions at European, national, and institutional level to speed up the EOSC implementation.	
Cloud Services for Synchronisation and Sharing (CS3)	6-8.03. 2023	Conference	Registration end: 1.03 Submission: 18.12.2022	Barcelona, Spain	The CS3MESH4EOSC project was an official supporter of CS3 Conference 2022. The CS3 community consists of providers, developers, and users of innovative storage and sync&share systems. Its services are integrated with user environments and higher-level application services. Furthermore, CS3 reports on the progress in data science at all levels, namely local laboratories, regional collaborations, and global science. CS3 applications range from innovative big-data analysis to science outreach and education.	https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/news-events/events/cs3-conference-0
EGI Conference 2023		Conference			The annual EGI conference is widely recognised as the venue that brings together like-minded professionals from the world of science and scientific computing.	

Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond	20.03.2023	International Seminar	Registration open	Gothenburg, Sweden	<p>A satellite half-day event in conjunction with the RDA 20th Plenary Meeting in Gothenburg, Sweden (21-23 March). It will touch on the main issues related to practical implementation of research commons. To this end, the event will attract an international audience of key actors involved in implementing research commons at disciplinary, regional or national levels, funders, data experts, technical managers, and in general.</p> <p>Panellists will open with global perspectives on implementation approaches, examining themes and challenges of assembling the main features of a research commons. The second part of the event will showcase examples of how RDA's diverse data community are tackling challenges.</p> <p>EOSC Future will also share examples, via its RDA Open Calls programme, related to the practical aspects of implementation such as: interoperability, discovery, upskilling.</p>	https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/rda-eosc-future-satellite-event-building-blocks-of-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond/
Wiosenne Targi Rolno-Ogrodnicze AGROMAR SZ	02.04.2023	National Fair		Marszew, Poland	Integrated plant protection use case presentation about the use case roll-up/presentation Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts	https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/wydarzenia/wydarzenia-wodr
Regionalne Targi Rolnicze Golaszyn	20-21.05.2023	National Fair		Golaszyn, Poland	Integrated plant protection use case roll-up/presentation presentation about the use case. Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts	https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/wydarzenia/wydarzenia-wodr
Krajowe Dni Pola 2023	3-5.06.2023	National Fair		Sielinko (near Opalenica), Poland	Integrated plant protection use case roll-up/presentation presentation about the use case. Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts, area of innovation	https://www.dnipola2023.pl/

EGU23	23-28.04.2023	International conference	<p>Registration: 08.03.2023</p> <p>Abstracts submission: 10.01.2023</p>	Vienna, Austria	<p>The EGU General Assembly 2023 brings together geoscientists from all over the world to one meeting covering all disciplines of the Earth, planetary, and space sciences. The EGU aims to provide a forum where scientists, especially early career researchers, can present their work and discuss their ideas with experts in all fields of geoscience.</p>	https://www.egu23.eu/
TNC23	5-6.06.2023	International Conference	<p>Registration: 23.01.2023+</p> <p>Submission:</p> <p>-Single Presentations and Workshops: 30.11.2022;</p> <p>-Demonstrations: 02.02.2023;</p> <p>-Lightning Talks & Smaller side meetings: 10.03.2023</p>	Tirana, Albania	<p>The largest and most prestigious research and education networking conference, TNC attracts a truly diverse audience of over 800 participants from more than 70 countries, representing national and regional research and education networks, schools and universities, technology providers, and many of the world's most exciting scientific projects. By bringing together decision-makers, networking and security specialists, identity and access management experts, researchers, academics and students, TNC offers a unique collaborative experience.</p>	https://tnc23.geant.org/about/

IFAC 2023	9-14.07 .2023	International Congress	Submission: -Discussion papers: 01.02.2023 -Final paper: 31.03.2023	Yokohama, Japan	<p>The Open Invited track - Human in the Loop of Artificial Intelligence in Smart Maintenance and Manufacturing Systems will be organised at the IFAC World Congress, the flagship event of the International Federation of Automatic Control, that takes place every 3 years.</p> <p>AI-driven human augmentation or industrial automation have seen many applications in maintenance and manufacturing. Much is expected to be achieved in automated manner from Machine Learning in industrial systems, leaving the possibility for properly integrating human knowledge and human capabilities insufficiently exploited. Yet, the application practice of Machine Learning and broader AI in Maintenance and Manufacturing provides ample evidence of brittleness of derived solutions in the face of limited or new data, changing contexts, or evolving situations. AI communities seek to address such challenges with approaches such as Transfer Learning. Employing human operators, workers, or engineering staff as a source of observation, knowledge, decision, or action is another example. The collaboration of human and non-human (AI-driven) cooperating agents in industrial systems is a further step. Considering the above, the effective integration of humans in the Machine Learning and Broader AI Loop for Maintenance and Manufacturing is the focus of this track.</p>	https://www.ifac2023.org/
European AI Forum	12.2023				<p>the European AI Forum has turned into a network of associations that want to make sure startups and innovators in Member States have a voice when it comes to building an AI regulatory framework.</p> <p>Our mission is to set the agenda on how AI is approached in Europe, both in terms of policy and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Our goal is to serve as a platform where entrepreneurs and policymakers get together to jointly determine the path forward for European AI innovation.</p>	https://european-ai-forum.com/

<p>ISC High Performance 2023</p>	<p>Monday, May 22 - 24 2023</p>	<p>International Supercomputing Conference</p>	<p>February 2, 2023</p>	<p>Hamburg, DE</p>	<p>ISC High Performance 2023 is an international conference and exhibition that fosters the growth of a global HPC community of technology providers and users. This growing community now includes machine learning, data analytics, and quantum computing practitioners. The first ISC conference was held in 1986.</p> <p>At this annual forum, the community comes together to exchange visions, ideas, and knowledge and dare each other to imagine a better tomorrow. ISC 2023 will be held from May 21 – 25 in Hamburg, Germany, and expects over 3,000 international attendees.</p>	<p>https://www.isc-hpc.com/submissions-project-posters-2023.html</p>
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IV. Dissemination Table

Type of activity	Related project result	WPs	Relevance to project	Title	When/Date	Event location	Partner responsible	Type of audience	Audience size	Link to event	Link to dissemination material
Computer Science course	general	All	general talk about the project	Lessons	October 2022	Bratislava	IISAS (with FIIT STU)	Computer Science students	177	Intelligent Data Analysis - Introduction to Data Science course https://github.com/FIIT-IAU/2022-2023	
Presentation	general	WP2, All	general presentation about the project	Meeting of the cluster of projects with EOSC Association in Brussels	30 September 2022	Brussels	PSNC	EC Projects, EC, EOSC Association	40	-	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1uBwY7yAVWpEbEkSVzeslDdTGt6yo8xDfRLCBumRCMc4/edit#slide=id.p1
Presentation	general	WP2, All	general presentation about the project	IberGrid	October 2022	Faro	PSNC	regional EOSC ecosystem	200	https://indico.lip.pt/event/1249/time-table/#20221012	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1B7UZvvGnHdXMJpGEYmXWwuUksipCulDu-zwYz_cTm8I/edit?usp=sharing
Presentation	general	All	general presentation about the project	EGI Conference	21 September 2022	Prague	KIT	EGI and EOSC community	200	https://indico.egi.eu/event/5882/	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1o5UXs-aORAKPfljHjL_ytR5hl76tqTQad-AXQBN3zyRs/edit?usp=sharing
Presentation	Integrated plant protection use case	WP2, WP6	presentation about the use case	Agroshow Bednary	September 2022	Bednary/Poznan	PSNC, WODR	Public, farmers, agriculture machinery producers, domain experts	180 (but whole event 200000)	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en/	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RMpVpyJWS2e9KW3pK7koBSE8R9WA9NuI?usp=sharing
Presentation				EOSC Symposium							https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/15ei7f1t5jeDPaIeV3S1Ns7SbduJe85kFMPs61jzloHQ/edit?usp=sharing

Talk	general	All	general talk about the project	Talk at INRIA	22 September 2022	Rennes	IISAS (with FIIT STU)	Computer Science researchers, teachers and students	70 (estimation)	SUPSEC: AI for supervision	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1qdqI_8A4jXiLDPVNpAp2OAGGONCUYGeODmRc4HzxeFeA/present#slide=id.p
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		SLOVENS KÁ AKADÉMI A VIED				https://www.ui.sav.sk/w/en/horizon-europe/#an_1_002 https://www.ui.sav.sk/w/horizont-europa/#an_1_002 (Slovak)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		KIT (SCC)				https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/research/16595.php https://www.scc.kit.edu/forschung/16595.php (German)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		Predictia				https://predictia.es/en/projects/ai4eosc https://predictia.es/es/projects/ai4eosc (Spanish) News: https://predictia.es/en/news/ai4eosc https://predictia.es/es/news/ai4eosc (Spanish)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA				https://www.grycap.upv.es/index.php/ai4eosc/
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		MicroStep-MIS				https://www.microstep-mis.com/web/about-us?tab=Projects News: https://www.microstep-mis.com/web/news/other/ai_for_the_european_open_science_cloud
post on social media	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		MicroStep-MIS				LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/microstep-mis Twitter: https://twitter.com/MstepMIS/status/1610925669436858373?s=20&t=OL_U63wuOxfXB4HREZPAMw Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/MicroStepMIS

												Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/p/CnByZ7Cl1QJ/
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		PSNC					https://www.psn.pl/projects/ai4eosc/ https://www.pcss.pl/projektv/ai4eosc/ (Polish)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		CSIC					CSIC: https://www.csic.es/es/actualidad-del-csic/el-csic-lidera-un-proyecto-europeo-para-impulsar-el-uso-de-la-inteligencia University of Cantabria: https://web.unican.es/noticias/Paginas/2022/octubre_2022/proyecto-ia-IFCA.aspx IFCA: https://ifca.unican.es/es-es/news/Paginas/IFCA-lidera-proyecto-europeo-impulsar-inteligencia-artificial-mas-avanzada.aspx
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		KIT (IIP)					https://www.iip.kit.edu/english/460_6075.php https://www.iip.kit.edu/460_6075.php (German)
post on local institutional webpage	general	All	general presentation about the project	AI4EOSC project	January 2023		WODR					https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/alias-projektv/ai4eosc